

[¹⁷⁷Lu] Lu-PSMA-I&T for Prostate Cancer Radioligand Therapy: A Radiopharmacy's Journey from Synthesis to Cost-Effectiveness.

Abstract:

Radioligand therapy (RLT) using radiopharmaceuticals targeting PSMA is a promising therapeutic option for patients with metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC). Among all available radiopharmaceuticals, [¹⁷⁷Lu] Lu-PSMA-I&T (Lutetium [¹⁷⁷Lu] Zadavotide Guraxetan) has demonstrated significant clinical efficacy but, to date, [¹⁷⁷Lu] Lu-PSMA-617 is the only commercially available radiopharmaceutical. Does in-house production of [¹⁷⁷Lu] Lu-PSMA I&T meet the specifications of Pharmacopoeia and the requirements needed for a quality and safe radiopharmaceutical, moreover improving accessibility and cost-effectiveness?

This study aimed to describe our experience with productions and related quality controls of [¹⁷⁷Lu] Lu-PSMA-I&T, analyzing the requirements of quality and safety along with general considerations on the cost-effectiveness and related sustainability from Health systems. The study showed, over several production batches, high radiochemical purity, confirming the reliability of such in-house production. The comparison between the costs demonstrates a significant decrease in the in-house production versus the procurement of a commercial product. Such significant decrease in the costs of radiopharmaceutical strongly enhances the sustainability of RLT in a tumor with increasing incidence such as the prostate cancer. Our results highlight the potential advantages of “in-house” production.

Keywords: [¹⁷⁷Lu] Lu-PSMA-I&T, prostate cancer, radioligand, in-house production, cost-effectiveness, RCY, RCP.